
Investigating the Effect of Organic Ash-Based Hybrid Binders, on the Mechanical Properties of Sustainable Concrete

Akwenuke, M.O.¹, Umukoro, L.O.², Akpokodje, O.I.¹

¹Department of Civil and Water Resources Engineering, Southern Delta University, Ozoro, Delta State, Nigeria

²Department of Civil Engineering, Delta State University, Oleh campus, Delta State, Nigeria

Abstract

This research was aimed at investigating the influence of hybridized bio-ashes (RHA and PPA), on concrete compressive strength. Six concrete samples (T1 to T6) were produced by partially substituting Portland limestone cement, with varying quantities of the hybridized ashes at levels of 15%, 20%, 25%, and 30%. The compressive strength (CS) of the concrete samples was measured in accordance with ASTM standards at 28 days of curing. Results obtained from laboratory analysis revealed that the two ashes have a significant effect on the concrete's CS. The maximum strength (24.59 MPa) was developed when the cement was partially replaced by 20% hybridized ashes (10% RHA + 10% PPA). This revealed that incorporating 20% hybridized bio-ashes in concrete, as substitution for cement yield concrete with enhanced potential to absorb greater compression force. The findings of this research have revealed that agricultural waste materials can be harnessed to produce green concrete, with better mechanical properties. This will help in addressing solid waste management and improving public health.

Keywords: Carbon emission, compressive strength, concrete failure, green concrete, organic ashes

Introduction

Concrete is one of the commonly used construction materials, due to its versatility in casting into different forms and sizes while retaining its mechanical strength. Concrete is largely produced from inorganic materials such as: water, sand, coarse aggregates (gravel) and cement. The utilization of concrete in structures, such as in buildings, bridges, roads, and dams construction, usually determines the type of materials, the concrete mix ratio, and the production techniques used (Akpokodje *et al.*, 2019; Ranatunga *et al.*, 2023). Concrete has high compressive strength, as well as thermal and weathering resistance, making it a suitable construction material in a wide range of climatic conditions (Nilimaa and Zhaka, 2023).

Cement, which is one of the principal components and a determinant of concrete strength, has many environmental drawbacks. Cement production requires a lot of energy, and emits a significant amount of heat and greenhouse gases, which contribute to global warming and other effects of climate change (Khaiyum *et al.*, 2023; Barbhuiya *et al.*, 2024). It has been documented that cement production amounts to about a quarter of the world's carbon (iv) oxide (CO₂) production, and CO₂ is among the major greenhouse gases. Due to industrialization and urbanization, the utilization of cement in the concrete industry has increased drastically, and the amount of cement required for the construction of structures is expected to increase by 23% in 2050 (Zhaurova *et al.*, 2021; UN, 2022).

Recently, there have been studies on the utilization of bio-cementitious materials as a suitable replacement for cement in the concrete industry. This aims to increase the environmental friendliness of the industry, thereby reducing the risks associated with cement production (Samad and Shah, 2017; Alsaed and Al Mufti, 2024; Owamah *et al.*, 2024). The use of biomaterials in concrete production gives rise to green concrete, which has a lower negative environmental impact, thereby contributing to more sustainable concrete (Agbi and Uguru, 2021; Patel *et al.*, 2024). Most of these materials used as substitutes for cement and aggregates are agricultural by-products. Their utilization in green concrete production is a sustainable approach to solid waste management and contributes to public health safety (Al-Mansour *et al.*, 2019; Hamada *et al.*, 2020).

The performances of bio-ashes in concrete production have been widely studied, but most of these studies were primarily based on the use of a single bio-ash, as a partial replacement for cement in green concrete production. Therefore, the main aim of this research is to develop a three-way hybrid material, by incorporating organic ash and other agricultural by-products in concrete production, with the goal of achieving acceptable mechanical properties suitable for building construction. The results obtained from this study will contribute to concrete technology, by enabling the production of more reliable and environmentally sustainable concrete, for various domestic and industrial applications.

Materials and methods

Materials

The fine aggregates (sharp sand) were obtained from the bed of River Niger in Delta State, southern Nigeria. The coarse aggregates (gravel) with a size of 20 mm, were obtained from a quarry in Ondo State, western Nigeria. Dangote Cement 3X (42.5R) was used for concrete production. The rice husk ash (RHA) and plantain peel ash (PPA) were obtained from the department of Agricultural engineering, Southern Delta University, Ozoro, Nigeria.

Methods

Concrete design mix ratio

The experimental design mix ratio used in this study is presented in Table 1. Additionally, the concrete mix design selected for production was 1:2:4 (cement:sand:aggregate), with a cement-water ratio of 0.6.

Table 1: The experimental design mix-ratio(%)

Sample code	Cement	RHA	PPA
Control	100	0	0
T1	85	10	5
T2	85	5	10
T3	80	10	10
T4	75	15	10
T5	75	10	15
T6	70	15	15

Concrete production

The batching by mass method was used to measure the constituents for concrete production. Additionally, the mechanical mixing method was used to thoroughly mix the materials to achieve consistency. Standard steel cubes (150 mm × 150 mm) were used to cast the concrete. Basically, the fresh concrete was poured into the mould in three layers, and the concrete was rammed 75 times - 25 times per layer - before the surface was flattened with a hand trowel. The freshly prepared concrete samples were covered with a plastic sheet, to reduce evaporation for 24 hours. After demoulding, the samples were cured for 28 days using the total immersion approach (Figure 1).

Figure 1: The curing of the concrete cubes

Laboratory analysis

The concrete compressive strength was determined in accordance with ASTM C39/C39M (2023) standard, using the concrete crushing machine shown in Figure 2. The concrete's compressive strength was computed employing the expression in Equation 1.

$$\text{Compressive Strength} = \frac{\text{Failure Load}}{\text{Cross-sectional Area}} \quad 1$$

Figure 2: The crushing of a concrete cube

Statistical analysis

This study's results were analyzed statistically using Microsoft Excel 2010 software. Each experimental test was conducted in triplicate.

Results and Discussion

Particle size grading

"The result of the sieve analysis of sharp sand is presented in Figure 3. It was observed that the fines content was less than 5%, indicating that the soil is predominantly coarse-grained. According to the Unified Soil Classification System (USCS), soils with low fines content and a well-graded particle size distribution are classified as well-graded sands (ASTM D2487, 2017). Well-graded sand often produce high-strength and long-lasting concrete (Ogunbayo *et al.*, 2021).

Figure 3: The sieve analysis plot

Compressive strength (CS)

The results of the compressive strength (CS) of the concrete, produced from different mix designs are presented in Table 2. It was observed that green ashes, had a substantial impact on the concrete's compressive strength. As shown in the results, the baseline (control specimen) had a compressive strength of 20.96 MPa, while treatment T3 recorded the maximum CS among the partial replacement samples, with a value of 24.59 MPa at 28 days of curing. The improvement in the compressive strength of the concrete produced from the bio-ashes can be linked to the pozzolanic nature of these materials. Pozzolanic materials react with the calcium hydroxide formed during cement hydration, to produce additional calcium silicate hydrate gels, thereby enhancing the concrete's mechanical strength and microstructural densification (Mohsen et al., 2023).

Furthermore, it was noted that as the volume of ashes exceeds a threshold (20% content), the compressive strength (CS) of the concrete tends to decline. This condition can be attributed to the large volume of ashes in the concrete matrix, which results in high water absorption capacity, thereby depriving the cement of sufficient water needed for hydration (Skariah Thomas et al., 2022). Additionally, an excessive ash volume in the concrete, will lead to poor interfacial bonding of the reinforcement materials (sand and gravel), resulting in concrete with weaker microstructural integrity, which will translate into a reduced capacity to withstand high compressive forces (Owamah et al., 2024).

The results obtained in this study aligned with the previous findings of Lakshmi (2017), Nilimaa (2023), Ranatunga et al. (2023), and Owamah et al. (2024). Generally, the results showed that the 20% inclusion of hybridized PPA and RHA, as partial replacement for cement, produced the maximum compressive strength, with the concrete exhibiting an enhanced load-bearing capacity. This affirms that using sustainable alternative bio-materials can significantly decrease reliance on inorganic cement in construction projects, ultimately contributing to ecological protection and alleviating the negative impacts associated with cement utilization.

Table 2: The compressive strength of the concrete cubes at curing day 28

Code	Compressive strength (MPa)
Control	20.96±1.32
T1	23.50±0.94
T2	21.60±1.16
T3	24.59±0.97
T4	19.76±0.48
T5	18.60±0.48
T6	14.88±0.48

Conclusion

The study was conducted to evaluate the influence of bio-ashes used as a partial cement replacement on the compressive strength of concrete. To achieve the goals of this study, different concrete samples were produced with varying volumes of cement, rice husk ash (RHA), and plantain peel ash (PPA) in a hybridized form. The samples were prepared and tested in accordance with relevant ASTM guidelines. It was observed from the compression test results that, both RHA and PPA, significantly influence the concrete's compressive strength (CS). The highest CS was recorded when 20% of the cement, was replaced with a hybrid mixture of RHA and PPA at a 1:1 ratio. Additionally, this study's findings indicated that including a higher volume of ashes (greater than 20%) had a negative influence on the concrete's compressive strength. Though this research outcome has revealed that hybridized green ashes can produce concrete with improved compressive strength, further studies are required to develop concrete with enhanced engineering properties across a wide spectrum of mechanical properties, through three-way combinations of bio-ashes.

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